

إنفاق الميسور في تاريخ بلاد التكرار

also known as “Affordable spending in the history of the country of recurrence”, “Infaq al-Maisur fi Tarikh Bilaad al-Tukrur”

By Jabir Musa, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina state, Nigeria

Entry tags: Uthmaniyyah, Religious Group, Islamic Theology, Text, Islamic Traditions, Islamic Revival, Islamic Caliphate of Sokoto, Uthmaniyyah Caliphate of Sokoto, إنفاق الميسور في بلاد التكرار

The Book was written by Muhammad Bello (the son of Uthman bn. Fodio), who reigned the eastern part of the Sokoto caliphate between 1817-1837 CE.

Date Range: 1781 CE - 1837 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).pr](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).pr)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Uthman, Muhammad Bello. Esay Expenditure Regarding the History of the Land of Tukrur . N.P: Makhtutaat Garbil Ifriqi, 1812.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://siiasi.org/digital-archive/sultan-muhammad-bello/infaql-maysuur/>

Notes: English Translation of the Text.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://searchworks.stanford.edu/view/5516897>

– Source 1 Description: Minna, M. T. M. (1991). The writings of Sultan Muhammad Bello and his contribution to scholarship in the Bilad al-Sudan. University of Maiduguri: Maiduguri, Nigeria.

– Source 2 URL: <https://pbs.twimg.com/media/DmuRfOIX4AAw0S5?format=jpg&name=360x360>

– Source 2 Description: An annotated Picture of Sultan Muhammad Bello.

– Source 1 URL: <https://pbs.twimg.com/media/DmuRfOIX4AAw0S5?format=jpg&name=360x360>

– Source 2 URL: By Anasskoko - Own work, CC BY-SA 4.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=101958894>

– Source 2 Description: Muhammad Bello.

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

Notes: The text was not kept in the author's tomb.

↳ Cemetery

– No

Notes: The text of the book was not kept in the cemetery, but rather in library for others to benefit.

↳ Temple

– No

Notes: The text was only kept in libraries and people's houses for their benefit.

↳ Shrine

– No

Notes: The text was not kept in the shrine.

↳ Altar

– No

Notes: The text was not kept on Altar.

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– Yes

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

Notes: various people kept it at home for their personal uses

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Many copies are kept in libraries, markets, and archives for the benefit of people.

↳ Specify

– Specify: copies of the book is available at market

Methods of Composition

– Printed with moveable type

Notes: But the original copy was written with ink

↳ Inked

– without Ink

Notes: The uploaded copy of the text is printed without ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Notes: The text was printed on paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: Paper

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The paper used in printing the text was prepared on a book-sized sheet.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

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Materiality

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Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

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Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: It was funded indirectly for the status of the author of the Book as the leader of one side of the caliphate.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: It finances the production of the text through ample support it gives to those teaching the book to others

- ↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?
– Yes
Notes: Leaders of the polity are considered religious leaders of the caliphate.
- ↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?
– Yes
Notes: Many of the political officials engaged in copying, reproducing, and compiling the text
- ↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?
– Yes
Notes: Political officials and religious leaders remained the same, hence overlapping in their work of each other.
- ↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?
– Yes
Notes: The polity enforced religious observance in accordance with the text.
- ↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?
– Yes
Notes: The legal code of the polity is derived from the text.
- ↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)..
– No
Notes: No economic preference is given in support of the text.
- ↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?
– Yes
- ↳ Present full-time?
– Yes
Notes: They devoted their time to production and teaching the text to others.
- ↳ Present part-time?
– Yes
Notes: Some are present on part-time bases
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

Notes: The religious specialist could come from both sexes

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

Notes: Religious specialty is open to any person

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

Notes: No preference of religious specialty to any class.

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Notes: They have other personal businesses in addition to religious specialties.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– No

Notes: No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– No

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 20000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 10000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 10000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 90000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Birthrate, Deathrate, Migration and Jihad.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 7000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 100000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 600000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Birth rate, Death rate and Migration

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Notes: The notion of the scholars goes along with that of the other audience.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: There is no mandate for proselytizing

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: Missionary is open to everyone

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The reward for proselytizing is reserved for hereafter.

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?

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Notes: The reward of proselytizing is promised to all adherents of the religion

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↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Notes: Coercion of proselytizing is not acceptable according to the text.

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

Notes: The text mentioned proselytizing

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Notes: Proselytizing is encouraged by the text.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: The text is considered official, for religious observance in accordance with the prescription of the text.

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

Notes: No oral recitation tradition is associated with the text.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

Notes: It could be altered once a mistake or error is found in the text.

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Yes

Notes: The text is open to alteration since was not divinely revealed.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Several schools are authorized to interpret the text in addition to its related books.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

Notes: Interpretation of the text can be done everywhere.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

Notes: Every learned person can interpret the text.

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– No

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– Yes

Notes: They usually settle to resolve disagreements while interpreting the text.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Qur'an and Hadith are considered codified canon of the scripture

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: The canons are not subject to alteration.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the cannon as it is currently understood?

– No

Notes: It is considered for their elaboration on the content of the scriptures.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

Notes: It was written in the Arabic language.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: The language of the text is considered foreign.

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: The language of the text is considered exogenous

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

Notes: It was written in the Arabic language alone.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Prophet

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

Notes: The polity uses the language of the text as a formal language.

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Notes: Fulani and Hausa languages are used to support the study of the text.

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Notes: Some people memorize some portion of the text and pass it to other people orally.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

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↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Angels and Jinns are presented in the text

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitoring is ever present in the text, for His ever vigil on the activities of human beings

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Notes: It prohibits it, except in due course.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

Notes: It does not allow it to be done recklessly.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

Notes: It did not allow it except in the due course

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: It doesn't have a desire for it but approves of human beings

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: It made it prohibited.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: Oaths are highly regulated and direct to avoid it unless necessary.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: It criticized it and encouraged people to strive hard.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: It prohibits its practice, as stated in the text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– Yes

Notes: It prohibits it among people.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Yes

Notes: It directed for its total avoidance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– I don't know

Notes: It is considered abominable and hence shall be avoided.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
 - Notes: Gossip was prohibited and directed for its total avoidance.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
 - Notes: The properties of believers are considered sacred and shall not be violated.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
 - Notes: It is directed for the proper ritual observance.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text mandated ritual observance on believers.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - Yes
 - Notes: It encourages efforts to convert followers of other religions to Islam
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
 - Notes: It directed for justice and fairness in economic affairs.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
 - Notes: It mandated personal hygiene on believers.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - Yes
 - Notes: It encourages people to its maintenance
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: It cares about justice to all.

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The text served as a manual for ritual services in Islam, such as Prayer, pilgrimage, Fasting, etc.

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text criticized celibacy based on a tradition from the Prophet (SAW) that checked it out from Islam

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text prescribed social norms that are approved, by Shari'ah.

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: Eternal deliverance is by the personal observance of religious duties.

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: The text does not contain any art or designation.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text established the reality of the day of judgment.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text encouraged lawful sexual activity with a special reward attached to it.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: It shall be in the hereafter.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Notes: The time is not specified.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– I don't know

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– I don't know

↳ At some other time [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Notes: they can not bring the end of the world by some acts.

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Notes: Divine judgment is stated in the text.

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: Eternal life in the Paradise

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Notes: Nothing could survive the eschaton

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: It set punishments for certain prohibited practices, such as Adultery, Fornication, Stealing, etc.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Notes: Some punishments could be done by the high god in the hereafter, while others are done by just judges.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Especially some identified angels.

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - Yes
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means
 - No
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly
 - No
 - ↳ Other
 - Yes
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure
 - No
 - Notes: Punishments in the hereafter are severe.
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?
 - Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?
– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?
– No

↳ Other form of punishment
– Specify: Punishment is stated to be in the hellfire.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
– No
Notes: It shall be in the hereafter.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?
– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?
– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?
– Yes
Notes: Versions of the text could vary with respect to the age and period of the copy

↳ Content of text?
– No
Notes: The content of the text does not change

↳ Ritual purpose of text?
– Yes

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?
– No
Notes: All versions of the text are considered proper.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: The text cleared away castration on the directives of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) against things that could limit the population of his people.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The text expresses a formal legal code applicable in the caliphate to establish justice.

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The text attached other formal institutions to the polity, such as the judicial, police force army, etc.

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictate by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The formal judicial system of the caliphate was regulated by the text.

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

Notes: The text institutionalized punishments for theft, fornication, adultery, and the rest of the grave offenses.

↳ Execution?

– Yes

Notes: The text formalized the execution of any found to have killed another person.

↳ Exile?

– Yes

Notes: Exile is being judged against those to have become a threat to society.

↳ Corporal punishments?

– Yes

Notes: Corporal punishment is being administered against those to have

committed fornication.

↳ Ostracism?

– Yes

Notes: The text judged the expelled of those to have remained a threat to the society of believers.

↳ Seizure of property?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed to the seizer of zakat dues from those who refused to pay

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text institutionalized rewards of public services

↳ Grants of property?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified certain categories of people entitled to the amount of Zakat and a tenth of booty.

↳ Social promotion?

– Yes

↳ Financial rewards?

– Yes

Notes: Financial rewards are being given to those who participated in the war against unbelievers.

↳ Implied financial rewards (tax exemption)?

– Yes

Notes: Those not to have possessed amounts due for Zakat are exempted from its payment.

↳ Grants of labor?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The text was made as a single book.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: It bestows reward of good deeds in the hereafter

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

↳ Other?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)
– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Many virtues are mentioned in the text.

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed fasting for its position as a pillar in Islam.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The text describes cultures that are having religious implications.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The text is a literary tradition that guided on religious services.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Notes: The text formulated the Hijrah lunar calendar, used in certain religious services of Islam

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

- ↳ Planting?
 - No
- ↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)
 - No
- ↳ Harvest?
 - No
- ↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?
 - Yes
 - Notes: On the seventh day of its birth.
- ↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)
 - Yes
 - Notes: The first haircut should be on the seventh day of his birth.
- ↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?
 - No
- ↳ Marriage?
 - Yes
- ↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?
 - Yes
- ↳ Divorce?
 - No
- ↳ Warfare?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Guidelines on warfare were made clear in the text.
- ↳ Funerary services?
 - Yes
 - Notes: To be done on the very day he died.
- ↳ Trade/commerce?

– Yes

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Notes: Festivals of Eid

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: 2

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: 10000

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?

– No

Notes: Food consumption is for all members of the community.

↳ Pilgrimages?

– Yes

Notes: Hajj and Umrah to the Holy Land of Arabia.

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

– obligatory for all

Notes: Pilgrimage is obligatory on any having chance and capacity of attending.

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– No

Notes: Many reasons are behind the existence of the text.

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

Notes: Pilgrimages are only associated with the religious events of Hajj and

Umrah.

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– Yes

Notes: It involves following the major routes of Arabia.

↳ Is the maintenance of the routes guided by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimages are conducted by walking

↳ Feasting?

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?

– No

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: The text did not require painful bodily alteration.

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

Notes: Burial is directed to be done in the cemetery.

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

–Specify: No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: The text did not require that, except on theft punishment.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text highlighted the essence of the Creator, Who controls other creatures' pate.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Suprem High God is the only diety worthy of worship

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: Existence of creatures indicate presence of the high God

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: Messengers

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Movement from one place to another

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 3

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 1200

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 3

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed for animal sacrifices on the day of Eid and expiation sacrifices at the event of Hajj.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits human sacrifices entirely.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: Attendance at five daily prayer congregations is mandatory.

↳ By the community?

– Yes

Notes: Attendance at five daily prayer congregations is mandatory for every individual.

↳ By specific individuals?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance and cleaning of the place of worship are highly recommended by the text.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Yes

- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?
 - No
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Maintenance of the place of worship is recommended by the text.

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: The text does not contain any art or designation.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: Versions of the text could vary with respect to the age and period of the copy

↳ Content of text?

– No

Notes: The content of the text does not change

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: All versions of the text are considered proper.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The text was made as a single book.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The text describes cultures that are having religious implications.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The text is a literary tradition that guided on religious services.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The text served as a manual for ritual services in Islam, such as Prayer, pilgrimage, Fasting, etc.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The text expresses a formal legal code applicable in the caliphate to establish justice.

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The text attached other formal institutions to the polity, such as the judicial, police force army, etc.

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

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– Yes

Notes: The formal judicial system of the caliphate was regulated by the text.

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Notes: The text institutionalized punishments for theft, fornication, adultery, and the rest of the grave offenses.

↳ Execution?

– Yes

Notes: The text formalized the execution of any found to have killed another person.

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Notes: Exile is being judged against those to have become a threat to society.

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↳ Financial rewards?

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↳ Implied financial rewards (tax exemption?)?

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– Yes

Notes: The text formulated the Hijrah lunar calendar, used in certain religious services of Islam

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

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↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

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- ↳ Marriage?
 - Yes

- ↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?
 - Yes

- ↳ Divorce?
 - No

- ↳ Warfare?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Guidelines on warfare were made clear in the text.

- ↳ Funerary services?
 - Yes
 - Notes: To be done on the very day he died.

- ↳ Trade/commerce?
 - Yes

- ↳ Festivals?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Festivals of Eid

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: 2

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: 10000

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

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↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?

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Notes: Food consumption is for all members of the community.

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Notes: Hajj and Umrah to the Holy Land of Arabia.

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Notes: Many reasons are behind the existence of the text.

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Notes: Pilgrimages are only associated with the religious events of Hajj and Umrah.

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Notes: It involves following the major routes of Arabia.

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Notes: Pilgrimages are conducted by walking

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– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?
– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?
– No

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?
– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Angels and Jinns are presented in the text

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?
– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?
– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?
– Yes

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or

aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text established the reality of the day of judgment.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

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Notes: Burial is directed to be done in the cemetery.

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

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↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

–Specify: No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

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Notes: The text highlighted the essence of the Creator, Who controls other creatures' pate.

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↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

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 - Specify: Suprem High God is the only diety worthy of worship
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 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No

↳ Can be hurt?
– No

↳ Can be tricked?
– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
– Specify: Existence of creatures indicate presence of the high God

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: Messengers

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Movement from one place to another

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitoring is ever present in the text, for His ever vigil on the activities of human beings

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Notes: It prohibits it, except in due course.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

Notes: It does not allow it to be done recklessly.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

Notes: It did not allow it except in the due course

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: It doesn't have a desire for it but approves of human beings

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: It made it prohibited.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: Oaths are highly regulated and direct to avoid it unless necessary.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: It criticized it and encouraged people to strive hard.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: It prohibits its practice, as stated in the text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– Yes

Notes: It prohibits it among people.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Yes

Notes: It directed for its total avoidance.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - I don't know
 - Notes: It is considered abominable and hence shall be avoided.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
 - Notes: Gossip was prohibited and directed for its total avoidance.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
 - Notes: The properties of believers are considered sacred and shall not be violated.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
 - Notes: It is directed for the proper ritual observance.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text mandated ritual observance on believers.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - Yes
 - Notes: It encourages efforts to convert followers of other religions to Islam
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
 - Notes: It directed for justice and fairness in economic affairs.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
 - Notes: It mandated personal hygiene on believers.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - Yes
 - Notes: It encourages people to its maintenance
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: It cares about justice to all.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: It set punishments for certain prohibited practices, such as Adultery, Fornication, Stealing, etc.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Notes: Some punishments could be done by the high god in the hereafter, while others are done by just judges.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Especially some identified angels.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

Notes: Punishments in the hereafter are severe.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Other form of punishment

– Specify: Punishment is stated to be in the hellfire.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– No

Notes: It shall be in the hereafter.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: It bestows reward of good deeds in the hereafter

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
- ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
 - No
- ↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

↳ Other?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: Eternal deliverance is by the personal observance of religious duties.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: It shall be in the hereafter.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Notes: The time is not specified.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– I don't know

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– I don't know

↳ At some other time [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Notes: they can not bring the end of the world by some acts.

- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
 - Notes: Divine judgment is stated in the text.
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: Eternal life in the Paradise
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - No
 - Notes: Nothing could survive the eschaton

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text prescribed social norms that are approved, by Shari'ah.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle)
– Yes
- ↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes

↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Notes: Many virtues are mentioned in the text.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text criticized celibacy based on a tradition from the Prophet (SAW) that checked it out from Islam

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text encouraged lawful sexual activity with a special reward attached to it.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: The text cleared away castration on the directives of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) against things that could limit the population of his people.

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed fasting for its position as a pillar in Islam.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: The text did not require painful bodily alteration.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: The text did not require that, except on theft punishment.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 3

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 1200

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 3

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed for animal sacrifices on the day of Eid and expiation sacrifices at the event of Hajj.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits human sacrifices entirely.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: Attendance at five daily prayer congregations is mandatory.

↳ By the community?

– Yes

Notes: Attendance at five daily prayer congregations is mandatory for every individual.

↳ By specific individuals?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance and cleaning of the place of worship are highly recommended by the text.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Maintenance of the place of worship is recommended by the text.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: The text prescribed guidelines for the regulation of bureaucracy.

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Notes: The text scheduled their activities.

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

Notes: The text regulated the activities of bureaucracy permanently.

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed the rest of the people on formal obedience and respect to the bureaucracy.

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

Notes: The text guided mutual interaction with other institutional bureaucracies.

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulates the entire activities of the place, and supporting income is inclusive.

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– Yes

Notes: The text set principles of leasing out land on justices.

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– Yes

Notes: The text set provisions on leasing out tools

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: Several expeditions were mentioned in the text.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

Notes: The text analyzed strategies for controlling military forces.

↳ Power to conscript?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified initiating new intake into military services.

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– Yes

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– Yes

Notes: The text advocate participation in any military campaign for the development of Islam.

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not accept the subjugation of the group by any exogenous group.

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: The society is popularly known as the Sokoto caliphate

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

Notes: The text enjoined the religious group towards payment of Zakat

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Notes: Payment of Zakat dues is not levied on any person to have possessed its amount.

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– Yes

Notes: The tax is linked to charitable giving for a special reward from the creator of all on the day of judgment.

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified special people entitled to the collection of farm produce zakat.

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulated places for civic function, such as administrative positions and other judicial posts.

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulate courts established for the establishment of justice in society.

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood

control)?

– No

Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

Notes: The text did not set restrictions on common transportation and movement of people.

Other form of regulation of public works?

–Specify: The text regulates centres of correctional services and management of war prisoners.

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention food production

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are standardized institutions for the teaching of the text in various towns of the caliphate.

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: The text institutionalized zakat and charity as famine relief

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: The text institutionalized Zakat and Charity as means of poverty relief.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: The caliphate has control over the production of the text.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed the establishment of an educational system that shall impart religious knowledge to the adherents.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No element of societal destruction in the text.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: The text advocates exceptional support and care for elderly people and the infirm.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Notes: The text made provision for skills acquisition education apart from religious education.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The text encouraged religious professionals to search for whatever education could support their life and religious services.

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text advocates other forms of welfare to the adherents in many forms.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The text did not restrict education to religious professionals alone as was left for everybody to search.

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not make any educational segregation between the male and female gender.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: Education is not gendered according to the text.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Notes: The text left teaching relationships without segregation.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed people with special respect to the teachers.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text

itself?

– No

Notes: Much emphasis of scholars on the reward of their duties is centered on the hereafter.

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